

Advertisement Effectiveness: A Review and Research Agenda

Prateek Maheshwari, Nitin Seth, Anoop Kumar Gupta

Abstract—In today's highly competitive, dynamic and technology driven business circumstances, marketers are under steady pressure to deliver the best. Organizations are continuously improving and upgrading themselves to meet customer expectations and demands. Technology has not only changed the way in which business is done in modern times but has also transformed the way to reach out to target audience. Marketers have identified most recent media options to communicate and convince potential customers. Numerous scholars have studied the research domain of advertising and have tried to recognize different measures of advertisement effectiveness in context of various media. The objective of this paper is to critically review accessible literature on advertisement effectiveness in context of varied advertising media, recognize major gaps in the literature and identify future research prospects on the basis of critical analysis of literature.

Keywords—Advertising, Advertising Media, Competition, Effectiveness Measurement.

I. INTRODUCTION

TODAY'S business scenario is characterized by high competition, dynamism and operational complexities. Competition has forced corporate to change and upgrade continuously due to rising customer expectations. Markets are cluttered worldwide and delivering finest to the consumers is at the top priority for each of the business unit whether large or small.

In such an aggressive business situation, advertising plays an important role in communicating with customers, both current and potential [1]. With the advent of new technology and development of various modern media, advertisers have discovered several innovative promotional options to lure target audience. The rapid proliferation of internet, cell phones, movies and video games has convinced marketing personnel to consider these as emerging media alternatives. Therefore understanding advertisement effectiveness in context of these emerging media choices is essential as it would contribute significantly to the productivity of advertisers in terms of effective allocation of their marketing budgets [1].

Prateek Maheshwari is a research scholar at GLA University, Mathura (U.P.), India and an Assistant Professor at Institute of Business Management and Research, IPS Academy, Indore (M.P.), India (Corresponding Author; Mobile: +91-9977802779; e-mail: prateekm@hotmail.com).

Dr. Nitin Seth is working with Indian Institute of Foreign Trade, New Delhi, India as Associate Professor in the area of Supply Chain Management (e-mail: nitinseth@iift.ac.in).

Dr. Anoop K. Gupta is Director (IASH) at GLA University, Mathura (U.P.), India (e-mail: anoop@gla.ac.in).

Fig. 1 Classification of Advertisement Effectiveness Literature

Hence, the purpose of present review paper is to understand the concept of advertisement effectiveness and to identify varied dimensions used to measure advertisement effectiveness with reference to different media forms. Numerous researchers have explored the area of measuring advertisement effectiveness with different views which is widely categorized in two broad categories for present study as shown in Fig. 1.

II. NEED FOR REVIEW OF ADVERTISEMENT EFFECTIVENESS

In today's competitive and dynamic business scenario organizations are witnessing tremendous pressure on account of increased competition, increased customer participation and increased consumer responsiveness. Organizations are struggling to find ways to deliver better to customers than their competitors. Traditionally, the organizations believe in increasing profitability either by decreasing product's cost or by expanding existing market [2], [3].

Researchers have highlighted that although cost reduction is one of the advantageous ways but there are limits associated with it. Therefore, increasing market seems to be more beneficial to organizations and researchers have proven evidences for positive association between increased advertising and improved market share [2]. The rampant growth of modern technology and latest communication methods has changed the way in which organizations advertise.

Marketers have made use of innovative advertising media viz. internet, cell phones, movies and video games to reach out to target audience and hence understanding advertisement effectiveness is essential. In this context, the subject of advertisement effectiveness needs a fresh understanding in the

modern business scenario and this study can help to identify major research gaps and future research prospects in the area of advertisement effectiveness.

III. ADVERTISEMENT EFFECTIVENESS: CONCEPTS AND ITS MEASURES

The early scholars in the area of advertisement effectiveness focused on theoretical considerations and developed conceptual frameworks to understand and measure advertisement effectiveness [4], [5].

Starch [4] suggested a conceptual framework to measure the probable effectiveness of a series of proposed advertisements before they are used while [5] examined three different aspects of effectiveness of advertising communication. Bendixen [1] developed an advertising effectiveness model and some practical sets of propositions that relates to long-term consumer behavior and have profound practical implications for the management of the advertising function.

IV. TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENTS

Numerous researchers have examined the effectiveness of TV advertisements with diverse perspectives [6]-[10]. Alpert et al. [6] in their study measured the impact of repetition on advertisement miscomprehension and advertisement effectiveness while [7] in their research focused on cross-national standardization of advertisements and measured the effectiveness of TV advertisements targeted at Chinese Canadians in Canada.

In a study, [8] compared the effectiveness of four telescopic advertisements with advertisements for same products using the traditional 30-sec TV commercial format and the infomercial format while [9] explored relative effectiveness of 15 and 30 second TV advertisements using intermediate variable viz. advertising recall, liking and correct brand identification. In another study, [10] incorporated AIDA model for measuring effectiveness of the TV advertisement for electric conservation in Isfahan city.

V. INTERNET ADVERTISEMENTS

Scholars have also investigated the area of measuring effectiveness of internet advertisements [11]-[14]. Newman et al. [12] studied banner advertisement and web site congruity effects on consumer website perceptions while [13] tested the effectiveness of a mouse pointer image in increasing the click through for a web banner advertisement.

Alijani et al. [14] explored various online advertisement factors that affect the recall of online advertisements and revealed that embedded videos, product price, product or services itself and credibility are key elements that makes consumers to recall online advertisements.

VI. IN-FILM AND IN-GAME ADVERTISEMENTS

With the advent of modern media options, the focus of researchers shifted from measurement of advertisement effectiveness for conventional media to films and video games. Most of the researches on effectiveness of product

placements measured it in terms of how well they were remembered [15]-[17]. According to [15], effectiveness of placements depends on the extent of conscious processing of the brand and its association in the memory.

Russell [16] tested the effect of different levels of plot connection on brand placements while [17] in their study revealed that execution style of placement had significant impact on the audience memory for the brand. Genre of the movie where placements appear along with characteristics of placements like the category of the brand placed, the mode, the kind of actor, his/her role in the film and integration had differential impact on effectiveness of placements [15]-[17].

It is evident that explicit memory measures such as recall or recognition are used in majority of the studies [18]. Thus researchers the use of implicit memory in testing advertising and brand placement effectiveness is also proposed by various researchers [18], [19].

VII. PRINT ADVERTISEMENTS

Measuring the Effectiveness of print advertisements is another area that has been widely researched [20]-[27]. Hanssens and Weitz [22] identified the specific characteristics of industrial print advertisements that are related to the effectiveness of advertising functions while [24] examined influence of variety of factors such as size of an advertisement, number of colors used, the product advertised and characteristics of the audience on recall and recognition of advertisements.

Patterson and Richards [25] developed a structural latent variable model to determine the affect of newspaper advertisement characteristics while [26] identified the factors predicting the effectiveness of celebrity endorsement print advertisements.

Keshari et al. [27] in their research explored the factors viz. attractive visuals, believability, informational content, relevance, memorability and persuasiveness that make service print advertisement more effective. Table I summarizes major research studies examined for the present review paper in context of varied advertising media.

TABLE I
MAJOR REVIEWED RESEARCH STUDIES ON ADVERTISEMENT EFFECTIVENESS

Author (Year)	[4]	[20]	[10]	[5]	[22]	[23]	[24]	[1]	[11]
Media Study Type	Conceptual	Print Survey	Print Experimental	Conceptual	Print Survey	Print Experimental	Print Experimental	Conceptual	Internet Experimental
Suggested Dimensions	Attention	Aided Recall	Type of Endorser	Precipitation	Recall	Attractiveness	Ad Size	Recall	Click Through Rates
	Interest	Action Score	Purchase Intent	Persuasion	Readership	Persuasiveness	Use of Color	Perceived Image	Copy Testing Measures
	Conviction		Believability	Reinforcement	Inquiry Generation	Credibility	Type of Product	Credibility	
	Memorable		Product Feature	Reminder	No. of Colors		Recognition	Familiarity	
	Action				Bleed		Recall		
				Ad Position					
				Presence of Model					
				Ad Size					
Author (Year)	[18]	[25]	[29]	[16]	[30]	[12]	[31]	[13]	[32]
Media Study Type	Film Conceptual	Print Exploratory	Print Experimental	Television Experimental	Television Survey	Internet Experimental	Film Experimental	Internet Descriptive	Print Experimental
Suggested Dimensions	Recall	Ad Size	Recall	Recall	Ad Length	Click Through Rates	Recall	Impressions	Recall
	Recognition	Color	Recognition	Recognition	Ad Frequency	Attitude Measurement	Recognition	Click Through Rates	Behavioral Intention
		Logo	Attitude Measurement	Attitude Measurement	Type of Product	Internet Usage	Purchase Intention		
		Consumer Preferences	Purchase Intentions	Modality	Recall				
		Purchase Intent	Involvement	Plot Connection	Recognition				
	Demand								
	Ad Border								
	Attitude Measurement								
Author (Year)	[19]	[33]	[9]	[33]	[34]	[35]	[36]	[37]	[27]
Media Study Type	Film Experimental	Television Experimental	Television Survey	Film Experimental	Film Survey	Conceptual	Television Experimental	Print Experimental	Print Survey
Suggested Dimensions	Recall	Recall	Recall	Type of Placement	Movie Genre	Attractiveness	Recall	Source Likability	Attractive Visuals
	Recognition	Recognition	Liking	Repetition	Mode of Placement	Credibility	Recognition	Source Credibility	Believability
	Choice Behavior	Likability	Correct Brand Identification	Consumer Attitude	Recall	Product-Celebrity Match	Attitude Measurement	Attitudinal Responses	Informational Content
	Consumer Attitude		Brand Execution		Recognition	Level of Involvement			Relevance
									Memorability
								Persuasiveness	

VIII. OBSERVATIONS, GAPS AND RESEARCH ISSUES

Based on the review of available advertisement effectiveness literature, it is clear that most of the advertisement effectiveness research studies are either experimental or questionnaire survey based. Students are taken as sample audience in nearly all the researches which is not appropriate and thus a debatable issue.

It is also evident that majority of the studies are done in USA, UK and other foreign countries. Typically in Indian scenario, the subject of advertisement effectiveness has not drawn much attention of researchers. Also, the subject of advertisement effectiveness is vague and perceived by varied researchers in different ways. Different dimensions are used in

different advertising media with reference to advertisement effectiveness. No generic ad effectiveness measures are available.

Furthermore, majority of the researchers have explored the area of advertisement effectiveness with two different perspectives viz. a) Dimensions on which Advertisement Effectiveness depends and b) Dimensions which are used to measure Advertisement Effectiveness. The survey of literature leads to some important research issues which require attention from academicians and practitioners. These issues are summarized below:

Research Issue 1: Despite of numerous researches on advertisement effectiveness, debate exists over the clear

definition of advertisement effectiveness with reference to specific media.

Research Issue 2: Majority of the advertisement effectiveness research is limited to the use of experimental or survey based research design. Can traditional research methods viz. content analysis, case study method, NGT or Delphi technique be used to investigate the area of advertisement effectiveness?

Research Issue 3: Advertisement effectiveness measures are product specific in context of different media in most of the researches. Is it valid in Indian context? If yes, then for what kind of products with reference to a specific media.

Research Issue 4: Even for a particular media, different researchers have used diverse advertisement effectiveness dimensions. Can some generic dimensions be used in case of a specific media for a definite product category?

Research Issue 5: Though numerous studies have focused on refining and deriving some specific ad effectiveness dimensions; none of the researches are seen in defining the interrelationships or linkages between the dimensions.

IX. CONCLUSION

An attempt is made through this research paper to review various studies on advertisement effectiveness and identify a range of measures used in context of a specific media. Select studies with reference to different media forms are summarized in Table I. It may be noted that the development of the advertisement effectiveness literature from 1964 to 2013 highlights the change in the focus of researchers from traditional to modern media. It is further observed that different dimensions are considered in different media for measuring advertisement effectiveness which adds to the complexities and vagueness of the subject. This clearly highlights the need of further research in the area of measuring advertisement effectiveness as summed up in previous section.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.T. Bendixen, "Advertising Effects and Effectiveness", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 27, No. 10, 1993, pp. 19-32.
- [2] G. A. Akerlof, "The Market of 'Lemons': Quality Uncertainty and the Market Mechanism," *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, vol. 84 (3), August 1970, pp. 488-500.
- [3] C. Shapiro, "Premiums for High Quality Products as Returns to Reputations," *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, vol. 42, no. 4, Mar. 1983, pp. 247-2608.
- [4] D. Starch, "Testing the Effectiveness of Advertisements", *Harvard Business Review*, 2009, pp. 464-475.
- [5] J.N. Sheth, "Measurement of Advertising Effectiveness: Some Theoretical Considerations", *Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 3(1), 1974, pp. 6-11.
- [6] Alpert *et al.*, "The Impact of Repetition on Advertisement Miscomprehension and Effectiveness", *Journal of Advances in Consumer Research*, Vol. 8, No. 2, 2001, pp. 130-135.
- [7] S. Hudson, C.L. Hung and L. Padley, "Cross-National Standardization of Advertisements: A Study of the Effectiveness of TV Advertisements targeted at Chinese Canadians in Canada", *International Journal of Advertising*, 21, 2002, pp. 345-366.
- [8] Reading *et al.*, "Effectiveness of Telescopic Advertisements Delivered via Personal Video Recorders", *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol. 10, No.6, 2006, pp. 217-228.

- [9] K. Newstead and J. Romaniuk, "The Relative Effectiveness of 15 and 30 Second TV Advertisement", *Journal of Advertising Research*, March 2010, pp. 68-76.
- [10] B. Ranjbarian, A. Shaemi and S. Y. Jolodar, "Assessing the Effectiveness of Electric Conservation Advertisements in Isfahan Channel Television", *International Business Research*, Vol. 4, No. 3, 2011, pp. 194-200.
- [11] J. Hofacker and T. Murphy, "World Wide Web Banner Advertisement Copy Testing", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 32, No. 7/8, 1998, pp. 703-712.
- [12] Newman *et al.*, "Banner Advertisement and Website Congruity Effects on Consumer Website Perceptions", *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, Vol. 104, No. 3, 2004, pp. 273-281.
- [13] K. Lees and J. Healey, "A Test of the Effectiveness of a Mouse Pointer Image in Increasing Click Through for a Web Banner Advertisement", *Marketing Bulletin*, Vol. 16, 2005 pp. 1-6.
- [14] Alijani *et al.*, "Effectiveness of Online Advertisement Factors in Recalling a Product", *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, Vol. 14, No. 1, 2010, pp. 1-11.
- [15] L. Percy, "Are Product Placements Effective?" *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 25 Issue 1, 2006, pp.112-114.
- [16] C. Russel, "Investigating the Effectiveness of Product Placements in Television Shows: The Role of Modality and Plot Connection Congruence on Brand Memory and Attitude", *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 29, Issue 3, 2002, pp. 306-318.
- [17] S. Lai-man and S. Wai-ye, "Predicting the Effectiveness of Product Placement: A Study on the Execution Strategy and Impacts on Hierarchy of Effects", *Oxford Business and Economics Proceedings*, 2008, pp. 1-25.
- [18] S. Law and K. Braun, "I'll have What She's Having: Gauging the Impact of Product Placements on Viewers", *Psychology and Marketing*, Vol. 17, No. 12, 2000, pp. 12-32.
- [19] M. Yang and D. Ewoldsen, "The Effectiveness of Brand Placements in the Movies: Levels of Placements, Explicit and Implicit Memory and Brand Choice Behavior", *Journal of Communication*, Vol. 57, 2007, pp. 469-489.
- [20] R. Manville, "How Much does an Industrial Logotype add to the Effectiveness of an Advertisement", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 29, 1965, pp. 57-59.
- [21] S. Schleifer and W. Dunn, "Relative Effectiveness of Advertisements of Foreign and Domestic Origin", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. V, 1968, pp. 296-299.
- [22] D. Hanssens and B. Weitz, "The Effectiveness of Industrial Print Advertisements across Product Categories", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. XVII, 1980, pp. 294-306.
- [23] B. Loken and B. Pitney, "Effectiveness of Cigarettes Advertisements on Women: An Experimental Study", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 73, No. 3, 1988, pp. 378-382.
- [24] Gronhaug *et al.*, "Factors Moderating Advertising Effectiveness as Reflected in 333 Tested Advertisements", *Journal of Advertising Research*, Vol. 10, Issue 4, 1991, pp. 42-52.
- [25] P. Patterson and T. Richards, "Newspaper Advertisement Characteristics and Consumer Preferences for Apples: A MIMIC Model Approach", *John Wiley & Sons*, Vol. 16, No.2, 2000, pp. 159-177.
- [26] D. Silvera and B. Austad, "Factors Predicting the Effectiveness of Celebrity Endorsement Advertisements", *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol.38, 11/12, 2004, pp. 1509-26.
- [27] Keshari *et al.*, "Constituents of Advertising Effectiveness: A Study of Select Service Advertising", *Journal of Services Research*, Volume 12, No.2, 2013, pp. 111-127.
- [28] Petty *et al.*, "Central and Peripheral Routes of Advertising Effectiveness: The Moderating Role of Involvement", *Journal of Consumer Research*, Vol. 10, 1983, pp. 135-146.
- [29] B. Wu and S. Newell, "Evaluating the Impact of Advertising Characteristics on Recall during the Super Bowl: A Two Year Comparison", *The Marketing Management Journal*, Vol. 13 (2), 2002, pp. 122-128.
- [30] T. K. Panda, "Effectiveness of Product Placements in Indian Films and its Effect on Brand Memory and Attitude with Special Reference to Hindi Films", *The IUP Journal of Brand Management*, Vol. 6(3), 2004, pp. 45-62.
- [31] D. Alain, "The Influence of Message Format on Effectiveness of Print Advertisements for Tourism Destinations", *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 26 (4), 2007, pp. 505-525.

- [32] K. Blonde and I. Roozen, "An Explorative Study of Testing the Effectiveness of Product Placement Compared to 30-sec Commercials" *Journal of Communication*, Vol. VI, 2011, pp. 36-58.
- [33] P. Homer, "Product Placements: The Impact of Placement Type and Repetition on Attitude" *Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 38 (3), 2009, pp. 21-31.
- [34] S. Kureshi and V. Sood, "In-film Placement of Product Brands in Hindi Films: Practice and Preferences" *South Asian Journal of Management*, Vol. 19 (2), 2010, pp. 37-60.
- [35] Z. Erdogan, "Celebrity Endorsement: A Literature Review", *Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol. 15, 2010, pp. 291-314.
- [36] R. Raj, "Role of Surrogate Advertisements: Impact on Recall of Parent Product and Attitude Formation", *Marketing: Delivering Value in Turbulent Times*, Vol. 44, 2011.
- [37] Cengiz *et al.*, "Source Characteristics and Advertising Effectiveness" *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 30 (5), 2011, pp. 889-914.

Prateek Maheshwari is a research scholar at GLA University, Mathura (U.P.), India. A first class graduate in mechanical engineering and post graduate in management from DAVV University, Indore (M.P.); he is currently working as Assistant Professor at Institute of Business Management and Research, IPS Academy, Indore (M.P.), India. He has guided many research projects at post graduation level and has more than six research papers of national and international repute to his credit. He has more than 6 years of teaching experience and his areas of specializations are Marketing, General Management and Operations.

Dr. Nitin Seth is an Associate Professor in Indian Institute of Foreign Trade, New Delhi, India. He has doctoral degree (Ph.D.) in the area of supply chain management from Indian Institute of Technology Delhi (IIT Delhi) and Post-Doctoral Experience (+6 Months), at GIZ/DIE Germany and Ecole Des Moines, Saint Etienne France (Programme Sponsored by Federal Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development, Germany). He has many research papers and articles to his credit. He is actively involved in the research on supply chain, total quality management, service quality and other related areas. He has about 17 years of experience in teaching and consultancy which includes three years of industry experience at middle level. He has delivered invited talks on several issues spanning SCM, operations management etc. at national and international level.

Dr. Anoop Kumar Gupta is Director (IASH), GLA University, Mathura (U.P.), India. A well renowned academician in North India, he possesses an MBA, M.Phil. and Ph. D. degrees from institutions of repute. During his academic stint he was conferred the Gold medal from Rohilkhand University for his outstanding performance. With a rich and vivacious teaching experience of more than 22 years; Dr. Gupta is an able administrator, multi-tasking, learned expert and a true mentor.